

Margot E. Fassler, *Cosmos, Liturgy, and the Arts in the Twelfth Century: Hildegard's Illuminated "Scivias"*, Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2023. Hardcover, xviii + 358 pp. ISBN 9781512823073

This is a book about the renowned Hildegard of Bingen (1098-1179), a nun and abbess, theologian, poet, and composer, Saint and Doctor of the Church. It was written by one of the foremost experts on her work, particularly in the musical realm. Although Hildegard has been the subject of study for over a century, has the most extensive body of work among composers of her time, and enjoys contemporary popularity to the point of inspiring current feminism, there are still many aspects to be clarified in her thought and activities.

The present work focuses on the relationships between cosmology, liturgy, music, and graphic illustration as they appear in Hildegard's treatise, *Scivias* ("Know the Ways [of the Lord]"), written in the 1140s. The illuminations in this treatise, with their peculiar forms and psychedelic combination of colors, synthesize the visions that underpin the author's mysticism. More than just a visionary, Hildegard was a seer; we could say that the foundation of her writing and her charisma as a leader of a religious community was an accepted and productive form of hallucination. Margot Fassler here provides an account of her extraordinary worldview, fueled by ideas shared by many in her time, and the originality of her expression in various media, consistent with the theological efforts of the century (especially Honorius of Autun and Hugh of St. Victor) and with influences that trace back to patristics and the 2nd century (Anonymous, *The Shepherd of Hermas*).

In *Scivias*, Hildegard extends and deepens, in a comprehensive manner, the pervading understanding of time and the universe through a geocentric, anthropocentric, and Christological vision that is, in reality, diametrically opposed to the scientific mode of knowledge. Particularly surprising, from a contemporary perspective, is the impact of the Trinitarian doctrine on the reinterpretation of the biblical narrative of the creation of the world: Jesus Christ emerges with a decisive and radical agency that compromises the possibility of an exegesis compatible with the Jewish tradition. Fassler, with exceptional erudition, reveals the intimate connection between the ideas in the treatise and its illustrations, whose meaning is initially quite opaque, even for those familiar with medieval iconography. In this regard, I would highlight the elegant explanation of "The Edifice of Salvation and Its Virtues" (Chapter 6).

For a reader interested in musical aesthetics, it is noteworthy how Hildegard appropriates the image of Paradise as a place of angelic concert, unfolding it into a cosmic narrative that ultimately results in the ethical demand for human sanctification. Influenced by St. Augustine, Hildegard sees time and the movement of the planets as a process triggered by the fall of a row of angels (Lucifer and his followers). This event transforms the remaining angels, pure sources

of light, into sources of sound, bursting forth in praise of God. However, in this celestial concert, one row remains missing. The creation of humanity serves a singular purpose: to fill this void.

Adam "knew all musical genres and had a resonant voice, sounding like the voice of the monochord." The voice of Adam before sin "had the sweetness of all musical harmony" (pp. 68-71, 259). In contrast, fallen angels are denied the ability to make music: in the liturgical drama *Ordo virtutum*, the Devil speaks but does not sing (p. 187). However, Adam is tempted by Lucifer and falls in turn, causing a convulsion in the universe. Unlike the fallen angels, whose fate is sealed, humanity has the opportunity for salvation by following the ways of the Lord, and thus retains the ability to sing in harmony. Gradually, it will produce enough saints to replace the fallen angels, restoring the primordial balance, which will simultaneously halt both time and planetary motion.

Hildegard self-identifies as a "new Adam" before the Fall and, in the spirit of her time, places the monochord, an instrument used to regulate intervallic proportions, at the core of the musical rationality of origins. Christ carries this rationality with Him, and it is transposed into the womb of the Virgin (pp. 97, 258). In fact, Hildegard views the Virgin not merely as a receptacle of divinity but as a focal point of sonic sanctity. According to her, the Holy Spirit makes music in the tabernacle of virginity. In the words she attributes to the Virgin, the beloved Son is the one who "constituted in my viscera every kind of music in all its tonal blossoms." The imitation of the Virgin by female monastic communities is therefore accomplished through music, divinely ordered according to the monochord, as a path to approach the angelic ideal and fulfill the cosmic purpose of humanity.

Fassler guides us through Hildegard's Christological cosmology, providing a profound and detailed understanding of how it is expressed in her illuminations, musical works, and liturgy (including the attire of her nuns). The importance of the Feast of All Saints becomes clear in the self-image of the nun community (pp. 71 and onwards) and in the work of the abbess herself (pp. 243-48). In Chapter 7, we can perceive how the liturgical drama *Ordo virtutum* embodies an innovative approach intimately related to *Scivias* (Table 7.1); the final chant, *In principio*, was also commented upon by Hildegard in her last treatise, *Liber divinorum operum* (p. 234).

Fassler, following in the footsteps of many musicologists since the early 20th century, recognizes that Hildegard's melodic style is decidedly non-Gregorian, which makes the rare quotations of Gregorian music particularly significant (pp. 196, 200-203). Her melodic composition arises from her unique understanding of modality, consistent with the German theoretical framework of the late 11th century. This framework favors intervals of the 4th, 5th, and 8th. She also disregards the traditional *octoechos* in favor of broader tonal areas centered around C (transposed *Tritus*), D, and E. The innovative character of Hildegard's melodies was acknowledged in her time by Odo of Soissons (p. 259).

The composition process emerges from the sonic imagination that accompanied her visions, with the poetic lyrics being added later to the "revealed" melodies. These melodies function through contraction and expansion of ideas, which may have motivic or formulaic nature and do not always align precisely with the musical phrase. The melodic range tends to be exceptionally generous, though at times it could be divided between two voices (intonation and continuation). Recent research has revealed their chronological evolution, suggesting that Hildegard had an unusually wide vocal range that diminished with age.

The unique nature of these melodies presents challenges in their analysis, which Margot Fassler does not escape. The music was transcribed in Hildegard's milieu using Germanic notation on a Guidonian staff (uncommon in the region), which fortunately allows intervals to be read but has some enigmatic peculiarities (the *quilisma* appears on unusual degrees and not always in the context of conjunct degrees). However, in a repertoire where the discussion is based on transcriptions into modernized notation, it is surprising that there is no discussion of the original notations.

In musical analysis, we have identified some issues. It is known that when comparing musical phrases, it is necessary to distinguish contour, structure, surface sound realization, the use of motifs and starting or ending formulas. From the same material, melodic variation can be more or less significant, and it is not always easy to draw the line between identity and alterity. However, the author tends to undervalue contour as a mark of melodic identity and presumes it even when the similarity is almost exclusively scalar. The formal alignment between phrases thus appears at times forced, relying solely on the initial motif or cadential formula to support the supposed phrase identity.

The potential discrepancies between the presumed and actual phrase relationships can be seen in the following examples: *Laus trinitati* (p. 98), where phrase 1" has no resemblance to 1'. *O gloriosissimi* (p. 118), where phrases 1.1 and 1.2 only share the cadential formula, and 3.3 has little in common with 3.1 and 3.2 beyond the initial motif. In *Virtus sapientiae* (p. 180), the second phrase, presented as a truncated version of the first, bears little resemblance to it. The alleged truncated or expanded versions of *In principio*, numbers 1 and 7 (pp. 228-229), respectively 1' and 7', have little in common, beyond the scalar structure, with the supposed model phrase. These examples highlight the complexities involved in analyzing and interpreting Hildegard's melodic compositions, where similarities can be misleading, and it's crucial to consider various musical factors, aside scale, intonation motifs or cadential formulas, to assess phrase relationships accurately.

That said, the richness of the content, the quality of production, and the graphic beauty of this book do not prevent it from having been poorly edited. There is nothing to criticize regarding typographical errors, as I only found one typo (*horthizantal*, on p. 190). However, everything else, as I will explain shortly, is a disaster.

The choice of endnotes is inappropriate for a clearly academic writing like this one, with multiple Latin translations, making verification more challenging. If the intention was to attract non-academic readers, there was no one to advise the author to reconsider the writing plan to enhance its readability. The only contextual information is provided in a very concise form on the inner flap of the cover. Reference is made to a complementary project available on the Internet, but the access link is not provided. The reader would need prior explanation of what *Scivias* is and what this treatise represents in Hildegard's intellectual trajectory. However, the introduction assumes in-depth knowledge of the character and her work, without any effort to facilitate entry into the topic for a non-specialized reader.

The book's structure, instead of initially engaging the reader, works against it. Chapter 1, "The Cosmological Background," is only useful as an appendix; in its current position, it appears as a detached digression from the main theme and may frustrate readers seeking to delve into the heart of the book. It should have been Chapter 2, "*Scivias* on the Rupertsberg," starting the book. However, even in this case, it should be preceded by a brief paragraph providing biographical context, outlining the essential facts alluded to scattered throughout the text. This would help readers understand, for instance, which monasteries Hildegard was associated with and during which period, her secretary Volmar's role, and many other details that most people, including musicologists and medievalists, might not be aware of. The initial paragraphs of Chapter 7, which offer a valuable framework for the cosmological innovations in 12th-century theology, could also find their place in the opening pages of the book.

The literary editor also failed to detect the numerous textual redundancies at the beginning of the book, which should have been eliminated. Additionally, there is an inconsistency on page 13, where the conceptual pair "cosmology/cosmogeny" is introduced and then replaced, without explanation, by "cosmology [in the broad sense]/cosmography." Redundancies extend to the footnotes, with the same Latin citation on page 291 (n.21) repeated on page 321 (n.67). There are instances where a citation from the original text would have been beneficial but is absent.

Even the figures in the book are not exempt from oversight. For example, Figure 3.1 (b) appears long before its discussion in the text and should have been separated from Figure 3.1 (a) instead of immediately following it. These editorial flaws do not diminish the author's merit but do hinder the reception of her valuable work.

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(English translation of review to appear in *Revista Portuguesa de Musicologia* 10, 2023)